

***AL-HISBAH*, ADVENT, DEVELOPMENT AND ITS FUNCTIONS IN THE MUSLIM COMMUNITIES**

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ABSTRACT

This paper attempts to expose the advent and development of *Al-hisbah* throughout history. *Al-Hisbah* as an Islamic institution is as old as Islam itself. Although a lot of people are ignorant of this vital Islamic institution, it began as a core Islamic principle because the message of Islam is entirely built on this principle. That is commanding virtues and forbidding evil. The importance of the institution of *hisbah* in an Islamic State and Muslim community cannot be overemphasized while participating in it by the Muslims is ever demanding despite some of the difficulties that seemed to be attached to it. Participation in ordering righteousness and preventing evil is the duty of every Muslim according to the dictate of the Qur'ān and Sunnah and other Islamic sources. This paper discusses the advent, development and functions of *Hisbah* in the Muslim community starting from the golden era of Islamic history to the present day. The paper uses qualitative method of data collection and analysis to trace the inception of *Hisbah*, its developmental stages and its function as a vital organ of the Muslim society.

INTRODUCTION

The importance of commanding virtues and preventing evils in human society cannot be overemphasized. The institution of *nisbah* being an integral part of the teaching of Islam, was commanded by the Book (*al-Kitab*) and Sunnah and practiced by the holy Prophet SAW first time in Islamic history when he established the first Islamic State in Medina, It continues for many centuries in the subsequent Islamic states after him. The institution has disappeared in many contemporary Muslim societies around the world especially among the Muslim majority areas of the northern Nigeria. This phenomenon has generated decadence in the Islamic behaviour and ethics especially among the youth in the areas of this study.

The problem at hand is that many Muslims are ignorant of the institution of *hisbah* to the extent of considering it as a kind of compulsion in religion that must be fought out of the place.

The duty of preventing evils and commanding virtues, even if it could be carried out at the individual levels of Muslims and groups, the power of those individuals and groups would be limited in carrying out this duty, unless it is sanctioned by the authority from where it would get the power needed for its enforcement and execution. Hence the establishment of institution of *al-Hisbah* is worthwhile.

At the eve of the third republic in Nigeria in 1999, some of leaders of political class in the Northern Nigeria, precisely in Zamfara state during the election at that time campaigned to implement Shari'ah (the Islamic Law) in its totality, if they were voted into power and won the election, so, they saw it honourable to fulfill their promises.

Islamic Law was pronounced, as part of the instrument for the application of the Law and the institution of *al-Hisbah* was established along the line.

The Concept of *Hisbah* in the Islamic Perspective

According to Abdul Karim Zaidan, (164-65), *Hisbah* literally is from the root *hasibayahsab* or حسب يحسب which means to count and record, some of the other words that may be taken from this root include: *Ihtasaba* means to count on somebody or to be sufficient by relying on somebody, it may also mean to show dissatisfaction on the act of somebody, it may further mean to let somebody accountable for something .

Technically it means ordering people to do good when it has been neglected and preventing evil when it starts to spread, so it is an act of ordering people to do good and preventing them from evil deeds. So, the Islamic jurists consider these acts *ihtisab* and *hisbah* so long as the person involved is doing that to seek the favour of Allah and His reward.

Proofs for legality of *hisbah* could be traced to the Qur'an and Sunnah, as every verses of the Qur'an commanding people to do good and preventing them from doing evils is considered as proof for the institution of *hisbah*. So, it has been mentioned in the Qur'an in different ways how the work of *hisbah* should take place. Sometimes the Qur'an makes it as duty of every believer for the nation to uplift the condition of people in the society and for the government to be successful in the act of governance.

According to K. Anwar (31), the term "*hisbah*" denotes some Arabic words of "*ihtisaba*", "*yahtasibu*", and "*ihtisaban*" denote several meanings; firstly, it refers to a reward from Allah (*talab al-Ajr*). Besides, it also indicates banning any

wrongful acts which are against the Sharīḥ. Citing Ibn Manzur, Anwar 31 stated that *hisbah* is “*masdar*” (a derivational word) from the word “*ihtisāb*” (hoping for some rewards from Allah SWT). In this context of the Sharīḥ, he elaborated that the term “*ihtisāb*” refers to the situation of looking closely into administering, overseeing, preventing or refraining from doing evil deeds. Concerning this matter, citing Ibn Khaldūn, Khoirul Anwar 31, opined that *hisbah* is a religious task, including doing good and struggling against harmful deeds.

On the other hand, from the word “*ihtasaba*”, “*yahtasibu*” refers to the acts of thinking any possibilities which may be materialized. Besides, it refers to the acts of making calculation or estimation of something. On the other hand, *hisbah* also derived from the verb “*hāsaba*”, “*yuhāsibu*”, and “*muhāsabah*”, carries the meaning of evaluating himself or examining one's conscience. To illustrate this situation, it has been narrated from the incident of Umar bin Al-Khattab, who has ordered Hatib ibn Abi Balta'ah to raise the price of the good sold by him or otherwise, he has to leave the place. Khoirul Anwar et-al, 33-34

In a nutshell, by defining the term *hisbah* as “enjoining good and forbidding evil”, it visualized the whole Islamic-oriented institutions and the public inclusively to accomplish such duties. Hence, it can be observed thoroughly that this kind of responsibility does not merely lie on the *muhtasib* per se, but rather on the whole individual Muslim as a whole. It is a mechanism of control or supervision of personal matters, family members, society well - being, good governance of an organization, or even the country affairs inclusively.

Halim , M. cited Muhammad Mubarak's opinion that *Hisbah* is an administrative oversight carried out by the government by assigning particular employees or officials to supervise moral, religious, economic, or social problems in society. Through *hisbah*, the state will realize justice and goodness based on the principles of Islamic teachings and traditions that are recognized and accepted in all places and times. Furthermore, according to al-Mawardi in Jeelani 2013, *Hisbah* has three essential roles: (1) Dealing with charges related to fraud and reduction of measurements or scales; (2) Dealing with charges related to fraud in commodities and prices, such as selling expired goods; (3) Handling the charges associated with delaying debt repayment when borrowers unable to pay. Therefore, the power of *Hisbah* is only limited to supervision to implement goodness and the prohibition of *munkar*, (*amar ma'ruf nahi munkar*). (Anwar 162)

In this case, *hisbah* duties could embrace ordering the deed in three contexts, namely: 1. Ordering deed related to the rights of Allah, for example, telling people to do Friday prayers and punish them if they do not do Friday prayers. 2. Ordering deed related to human rights, for example, telling people to pay the debt when they are able to pay immediately. 3. Ordering deed related to the shared rights between God and human rights. For example, telling parents/guardians to

encourage their girls to marry men who have balanced *kuf'u* (comparable), this also applies equally to women who have divorced with their husbands.

There are numerous verses in the Holy Qur'an, as well as narrated Hadith, which vehemently emphasized on the meaning of *hisbah* as the function is mostly based on the fundamentals of encouraging and enforcing virtues and discouraging and preventing of vices.

يَا أَيُّهَا الَّذِينَ ءَامَنُوا لَا تُحَرِّمُوا طَيِّبَاتِ مَا أَحَلَّ اللَّهُ لَكُمْ وَلَا تَعْتَدُوا إِنَّ اللَّهَ لَا يُحِبُّ الْمُعْتَدِينَ وَكُلُوا مِمَّا رَزَقَكُمُ اللَّهُ حَلَالًا طَيِّبًا وَاتَّقُوا اللَّهَ الَّذِي أَنْتُمْ بِهِ مُؤْمِنُونَ ۝ ۸۸

O you who believe! do not forbid (yourselves) the good things which Allah has made lawful for you and do not exceed the limits; surely Allah does not love those who exceed the limits..... 88. And eat of the lawful and good (things) that Allah has given you, and be careful of (your duty to) Allah, in Whom you believe. 88. And eat of the lawful and good (things) that Allah has given you, and be careful of (your duty to) Allah, in Whom you believe.

وَلَتَكُن مِّنكُمْ أُمَّةٌ يَدْعُونَ إِلَى الْخَيْرِ وَيَأْمُرُونَ بِالْمَعْرُوفِ وَيَنْهَوْنَ عَنِ الْمُنْكَرِ وَأُولَٰئِكَ هُمُ الْمُفْلِحُونَ

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104. And from among you there should be a party who invite to good and enjoin what is right and forbid the wrong, and these it is that shall be successful. (Al-Imran: 104)

There are many traditions of the Prophet SAW emphasizing on the encouragement and enforcing virtues and also preventing of evils and vices in the society:

عن أبي سعيد الخدري رضي الله عنه قال: سمعت رسول الله صلى الله عليه وسلم يقول: "من رأى منكم منكراً فليغيره بيده، فإن لم يستطع فبلسانه، فإن لم يستطع فبقلبه وذلك أضعف الإيمان" ((رواه مسلم)).

Abu Sa'id Al-Khudri (May Allah be pleased with him) reported:

Messenger of Allah (ﷺ) said, "Whoever amongst you sees an evil, he must change it with his hand; if he is unable to do so, then with his tongue; and if he is unable to do so, then with his heart; and that is the weakest form of Faith" Muslim

By referring to the above hadith, it has been explained by the Prophet that it is an obligation imposed upon every individual Muslim to prevent the commission of any sinful act by using any means, including preventing the evil with the power

that we have or we advise him or warning the evil doer. Finally, evil could be stopped through the heart, for instance, by not giving any help or cooperation to get involved, which indicates our disagreement with that evil.

Nevertheless, this action has been perceived as the lowest degree of *Īmān* in the process of implementing the notion of Islamic teachings against any kinds of mischief. Similarly, the Prophet ordained the necessity of upholding truth and fighting against any evil. Hence, with regards to hadith mentioned above, it can be understood that *hisbah* is recognized as been part of the Sharīḥah injunctions to be enforced as an obligation, respectively.

2.6 Relevance of *Hisbah* in Islam

Abdul Karīm Zaidān discussed the institution of *hisbah* extensively in his work on dawah. According to him, *Hisbah* has an important role to play in an Islamic society as it is an act of commanding good generally and preventing evil and this is one of the most important duties of the Prophet S.A.W and also the duty of an Islamic community after the demise of the Prophet .

Hisbah has many evidences from the quranic point of view and the Hadith of the noble Prophet Muhammad (SAW)

He posited that the followings are considered as pillars of *Hisbah* by the Islamic jurists:

- a- The executor of *hisbah*, is the person who stands as the first pillar of *hisbah* and he is called *Muhtasib* meaning; the commander of *hisbah*. He is the one to lead the group that will go out to prevent evil and order righteous deeds among the people, though the *Muhtasib* could be divided into two; one appointed by the ruler who is accountable to the government, and the other *Muhtasib* is the one that does the work of *hisbah* on a religious ground and has no duty to report to any authority as he is doing the work of *hisbah* to earn a reward from Allah and not to earn salary or gift.
- b- The *Muhtasib* that is appointed by government has power to employ people who will assist him in the execution of his duty and he has to pay wages to those being employed.

It is essential that the *Muhtasib* and those that are working with him should not act as judges, their duty is to correct the evils or change the evil wherever and whenever it appears and to enforce righteous deeds whenever there is need.

The *Muhtasib* cannot ask the evildoers for evidence on whatever they have been accused of.

As it is known that a judge cannot interfere in the issue of evil and righteous deeds in the society except when such cases are brought to his court, the *Muhtasib* can do that and he has the authority even as far as punishing an accused person even if the case has not been brought to his office, to the extent that he can order people to establish prayers at their times and order individuals to attend congregation in the mosque, he can also punish those who delay prayers out of its times.

It is essential that the *Muhtasib* and his men should fulfil certain conditions to qualify for duty of *hisbah*. These include being a responsible person which means being sane, matured, being a Muslim, being appointed by the Imam and being a just person. The *Muhtasib* must have enough knowledge about *Shari'ah* so that he would be able to identify what are considered as righteous and evils deeds in Islam, likewise if his duty as a *Muhtasib* has to do with commerce and trading, he must have sufficient knowledge in that area. He must also have the ability to do the work of *hisbah*

1. Persons upon which *hisbah* could be carried out are the generality of the people in the society. This includes: the people of authority in the government, the relatives of the *Muhtasib*, non-Muslims in the society, the judges and the artisans, it could also include merchants and companies that produce goods in the country.
2. The topics of *hisbah* include any evil in the society that is apparent and righteous deeds that are needed. Prevention of the evil and ordering righteous deeds by the *Muhtasib* must be taken immediately without any delay and without any dispute and that evil should be considered as evil islamically as it embraces the issue of belief, worships, transactions, treatment of diseases and the likes.
3. The execution of *hisbah*:

Hisbah could be executed by the *Muhtasib* using any possible means to remove the evil by his hands which may lead to breaking the bottles of liquors, destroying contraband goods, pushing the evildoers with force in the process of preventing such evil. In essence, he could remove the evil by force if necessary, he could do that by his command if that will suffice, he could do that also by merely advising the evildoer and guiding him or her to righteous deeds, he could also scold the evil doer and even abuse him if necessary, he could also intimidate the evildoer and lastly he could do that by his heart if he lacks power to do what we have mentioned above. (Abdul Karim, 164-192)

2.7 Historical Development of *Hisbah* Institution

Though the duty of encouraging good deeds and preventing evil ones is an individual obligation of Muslims, throughout history, Muslim states had

perceived themselves as empowered to establish arrangements to oversee its implementation or at least coordination of individual efforts in this line. Hence, some institutions have been established in order that Allah's orders and prohibitions can be applied in daily life.

For instance, *zakāt* collection officers and *zakāt* institutions have emerged in order for *zakāt* to become widespread in society. In a similar vein, administrations of Islamic states established

Hisbah agency whose duties are carried out by carefully selected people according to a clear set of conditions in order for its activities to be properly managed by the state, in order for the state to coordinate its efforts in discharging its responsibility of enjoining good and forbidding bad (Dogarawa, 51)

"The main mission and purpose of the *Hisbah* institution, since its outset in the early Islamic state in the Prophet's time, is to protect members of society from deviance, preserve their faith and guarantee the welfare of the people in both religious and worldly matters according to the Islamic and tradition-based law. Further, this institutions has served as a control mechanism to maintain the order of social life, so that everyone will enjoy security and the fulfillment basic

needs (Al-Hamar,; Abdullah, Dogarawa, 51-63)

Development of *Hisbah* institution has had an evolutionary stage, in that, while *Hisbah* activities were mainly conducted through preaching and advising individuals in order to encourage moral behavior and to discourage immoral ones at first, over time, the *Hisbah* activities went beyond religious preaching towards taking care of general social issues El-Sergany, 2010. While, after the Prophet, the first four caliphs personally performed this duty, in the later period when government affairs became complicated and multi faceted, a special officer was appointed to perform the duty of *Hisbah*, called *Muhtasib*. In its maturation stages, this institution were empowered to deal with different social issues from maintenance of cleanliness of roads to animal welfare, from health care to preventing teachers from severe beating of children, from preventing alcohol and narcotics to become widespread to preventing fornication and adultery.

As the social tasks of *Hisbah* institution continued to grow over time, The *Hisbah* institution had become a key institution for Muslim societies under different names and diverging missions depending on the social needs and visions of statesmen in Muslim States; up to late last a few centuries. However, when Muslim states began to lose their strength since 18th century and most of sovereign Muslim countries had become dependencies of Western powers under the colonialism trend, *Hisbah* institution suffered a drastic decline.

Khan, and Dograwa, 64 are of the view that where the institution continues to exist, it further disintegrated into a number of departments and in some places

remained an ineffective appendage of the state organs as many of its functions were reassigned to non-religious state departments or autonomous institutions in such Muslim lands of Ottoman Turkey, Iran and Egypt. An exception was the Saudi Arabia, where she disintegrated tasks and functions of *Hisbah* institution into two main groups and retained intact the religious wing of the *Hisbah*, while distributing its secular functions to different public organizations and ministries.

It is worth to mention here that a number of European states have adopted the *Hisbah* system when they witnessed its functioning style during the course of Crusades and when they develop close relations with Muslim countries such as the Ottoman State, while the importance of *Hisbah* was in decline in Muslim countries. For instance, when European powers which came to the Middle East for Crusades occupied Jarusalem in 11th and 12th Centuries, they decided to retain the *Hisbah* system and allowed *Hisbah* officers to check markets and shops, to prevent fraud goods to be brought by vendors and peddlers to the market; and make sure that basic necessities such as bread and oil are always available in the market. (Khan, 57)

Later, some functions of the *Hisbah* institution were transferred to the West gradually, under different names and formats. A well-known institution which was established through emulating some functions of *Hisbah* is the Office of Ombudsman. The *Hisbah* institution had continued to be a central institution during the history of Islamic rule, as it had been the core ingredient in the management and development of the Islamic nation, particularly during the Abbasid era. “During the Fatimiyyah period, the importance of the institution of *hisbah* become more obvious in terms of enforcing the prescribed rules and regulations. In fact, *muhtasib* is not merely investigating business places and determining the proper weights and measurements but also ensuring that there must not be overloaded items being carried out by the traders. (Khan, 57-87)

In addition, the scope of *muhtasib*'s duties also was extended due to the fact that they also were responsible in maintaining the morality of the subjects so that the members could live peacefully in the society. Later, enforcement officers' institutions like police force were set up in order to impose upon, together with enforcing the prescribed penalties among the wrongdoers”(Md Shah, et al, 386-394. Over time, however, the prestige of the *Hisbah* institution was decreased, particularly when the government weakened during the early 10th/16th century in *Mamlūk* reign of Egypt.

2.8 Role and Functions of *Muhtasib*

One of the main aims of Islam on governing the affairs of state and society is to bring a stable and secure society filled with love, whereby the members of society work together in righteous activities. Therefore, Muslim jurists have put some principles to preserve the five universal

needs of mankind i.e. faith, life, reason, lineage, and wealth.

These principles also provide main *raison d'être* of the *hisbah* institution, in that it has to function to ensure that this mission is properly carried out.

Saleh lists the main goals of *hisbah* as follows:

- a. Protecting religious values and encouraging religious-based deeds
- b. Preparing a righteous society by supporting and cultivating high moral standards and by combating immoral behavior(12).
- c. Preparing the righteous believer to be concerned with the affairs of his society and to work for its welfare.
- d. Providing the members of society with a constant monitoring of their activities, supporting and strengthening positive activities, while combating and preventing corrupt ones.

As *Hisbah* is an important social/religious/economic institution, Islamic law has described a special procedure and determined some qualifications for the appointment to the post of *Muhtasib*. “The *Muhtasib* is to be a free Muslim male with a high degree of integrity, insight, reverence and social status. He is supposed to be a scholar of the state affairs, law and religion... with a high degree of in- depth knowledge in the social customs and morals. Among the qualities of *Muhtasib*, knowledge, kindness and patience are considered to be of prime importance. *Hisbah* as an important institution, can investigate matters which affect the morality of the public” (Khan, 50).

As it performs quasi-judicial functions, although not forming a part of the judiciary, but embraces all aspects of life, whether worldly or religious, being an independent and impartial institution is a vital feature of *Hisbah*. Not only *muhtasib*, but also any people which work for the Office of *Hisbah* need to carry some individual moral, social values and commercial dealings, as *Hisbah* is supposed to supervise the whole economic enterprise.

According to Khan, 56 and some other scholars duties of *Muhtasib* include:

1. To command the fulfilment of trusts;
2. To prohibit all evils and misdemeanour, particularly lying and dishonesty. His job is to make sure that there is no dishonesty with regard to weights and measures, manufactured goods, credit transactions and trade in general;
3. To keep a check on the practice of hoarding.
4. To prevent the instances of fraud in all sorts of transactions by laying down specific and detailed rules for different traders.

5. To keep an eye on all trade and to make sure that those who work in a trade are well qualified for the job and know the rules of the law and regulations in respect with businesses.
6. To ensure that all the needs of people are taken care of.
7. To keep an eye on the conduct and honesty of those merchants who deal with lady customers.
8. To check business frauds and adopt policy for its eradication.
9. To take notice of other market imperfections such as the practice of intercepting of goods before they reach the market, in order to protect interest of the consumers and public at large. (Hamza 29)

2.9 Major Functions of Hisbah Institution

Explaining the functions of institution of *Hisbah* Hamza 28 was of the view that it developed over the centuries and its scope and functions, of its chief (*muhtasib*) were step by step established. Further, in Islamic societies such as Malaysia to Saudi Arabia from Ottoman Turkey to Morocco its functions varied in their structure and complexities, as Muslim societies in different regions of the world has had to a some extent different kinds of problems. Hence, as even the society of a region or a country does not remain static, the establishment of *Hisbah* organization, functions and modus operandi of the institution as well as the steps taken by the *hisbah* officials are deemed to change. For instance, while in some countries the institution of *Hisbah* is preserved in its entirety to a great extent; in most cases tasks accomplished by the officials of the ancient Islamic states under the institution of *hisbah* have been reassigned to the judiciary and to the police organizations. Furthermore, traditional/ historical functions of *Hisbah* institution would have contemporary implications in both Muslim and, surprisingly, non-Muslim countries, as the functions performed by *Hisbah* officials have been real needs of the society, whether medieval or contemporary, and the economy of all kinds. (Hamza 29-30)

Traditional functions of *Hisbah* institution could be evaluated in three groups, namely;

- a. market regulation and enhancement of ethical business
- b. mediating between state and society
- c. preserving public interests through commanding (enforcing /advising) goods and forbidding the evil deeds and behaviours within the society.

These functions can be translated into the contemporary world taking the tasks and functions the institution into account such as Ombudsman office, Community

Policing, Market Regulator Agency, Religious Affairs Advisor, Social Worker and Law Enforcement officer.

a. Supervision of Markets

It was the leading area of *hisbah*, and the earliest available writing in the form of a book *Ahkām al-Sūq* (market regulations) on the *hisbah* is by the third century Andalusian jurist Yahyā b. ‘Umar Kinānī (/828-902 CE) clearly explored this function of *Hisbah* institution. The official which had worked on the name of *Hisbah* institution with the task of market supervision was named as *sāhib al-sūq* (market director). His prime responsibility was to put standards in weights and measures used in markets and ensure the use of standard weights and measures. “He used to ensure that commodities were sold at approved prices and prohibited the sale of wine, indulgence in usury and gambling. He had to look after the interests of all those concerned in trade and business and to ensure no one was duped or illegally benefited.

b. Promotion of religious life and facilitating the practice of Islamic Worships

In its early stages, a major responsibility of the *Hisbah* institution was to ensure that people were regular in offering five-times obligatory prayers at proper timings. However, the role of *Hisbah* was not only to encourage Muslims to do their prayers, but more importantly, to ensure maintenance of mosques, cleanliness around them and the appointment of *Mu’azzins*.

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Some historians acknowledge that *Hisbah* officials have a significant role in such issues as observance of Friday congregational prayer and *ilds* (two annual religious festivals) and payment of *zakāt* by rich and wealthy people. (Hamza 31)

C. Protecting Public Interests and the Rights of Weak Segments of the Society

Another mission of *Hisbah* institution was to guard the public interest by and large. The institution had served public interest through fighting the malpractices of the market, like hoarding and corruption.

The *Hisbah* institution and its chief, *muhtasib*, were responsible for protecting the rights of disadvantageous and relatively weaker segments of society (those who are handicapped, daily wage-earners and children etc.) against the excesses of the rich and powerful people. This role could be considered as an early version of social work in many cases, *Hisbah* was also empowered to deal with other social aid issues either individually providing social aid to poor or providing arbitration between rich and wealthy charitable people and poor and needy. (Hamza 32) According to Islamic principles, humanity is not allowed to do everything to the living things and must only take their lives if necessary.

Furthermore, there are Islamic restrictions on manipulating animals, such as limited hours of work. Similarly, hunting of young birds for pleasure is forbidden by Islam. From the Islamic viewpoint, animals represent Allah's might and wisdom, and humanity must pay attention to their health, feed and living conditions. Islam determines the living costs of animals and orders humanity to respect and not to abuse them. Therefore, *Hisbah* officials were empowered to protect animal rights and to ensure betterment of living conditions of both domestic and wild animals as well as to warn those who committed cruelty to animals. Feener, 2012 pp. 275-311

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e. Community policing activities

Traditionally, the mission of *Hisbah* institution has been certain type of community policing, in order to contribute to moral development of the society. However, *Hisbah* officials are not police officers themselves. Although there is a strong relationship between police and *Hisbah* organizations, the relationship here is complementary, in that *Hisbah* produces and presents to other authorities mainly preventive measures to be taken against the acts which disrupt order and morale of the society such as violence, crimes against women and child abuse.

The *Hisbah* officers have to constantly be in contact with local judges, police authority, local branches of the central government, local government, civil society organizations and other branches of administration in order to prevent crimes and bad behaviors in both market and society. Although *Hisbah* institution has also power render necessary assistance to the police and other security agencies especially in the areas of deterrence, revealing and reporting of crimes in such *Shari'ah*-implementing countries as Saudi Arabia and some states of Nigeria and Indonesia, Garba, 20, is of the view that this practice is still under discussion on how the Office of *Hisbah* is expected to discharge its duties particularly in the area of forbidden evil is quite – reflective of the inherent gentility, fairness, politeness and wisdom. By this, it can safely be stated that, the characteristics of the concept of community policing are inherent in the Islamic Institution of *Hisbah* in the area of performing their functions” (Garba, Hakeen et-al. 25).

Conclusion

This paper is an insight into the advent of the institution of *Hisbah*. It is evidently clear that the institution of hisbah began during the advent of Islam as an institution that was later taken as a responsibility at individual and community levels. The companions of the Prophet who were the direct recipient of the message of Islam took this responsibility to the next generation. Hisbah was subsequently passed across generations of Muslims up to this day. The paper made it explicit that the institution of Hisbah is primarily based on commanding

virtues and restraining evils. Therefore it could be concluded that Hisbah is a core aspect of Islam as a total way of human life. It is observed that the absence of this institution in today's society is a major reason for degeneration of social order. Consequently, it is recommended that every Muslim community should endeavour to establish this important institution for the wellbeing of the society.

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